

STATIC ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH BEAMS USING VARIABLE STIFFNESS MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The bending behavior of sandwich beams using an axially graded honeycomb core is investigated using a layer-wise sandwich beam model. Assumptions are made that both face sheets behave as Euler beams and the core is modelled with a first order shear deformation theory. With geometrical compatibility enforced at both upper and lower skin/core interfaces applied, the beam's field functions are reduced to only three, namely the extensional, transverse and rotational displacements at the mid-plane of the core. Governing formulations are developed via the minimum potential energy principle and the Ritz method is used to obtain an approximate solution. Geometrically nonlinear effects are considered in the present formulation by introducing von Karman strains into the face sheets and core. A variety of geometries and boundary conditions including clamped-clamped fixed and clamped-free cantilever type beams have been investigated using the present formulation. Results show that the proposed model provides accurate prediction of displacements and stresses, compared to three dimensional finite element analysis. The "Zig-Zag" effect shown in axial stresses through the beam thickness is also efficiently captured. Furthermore, with the proposed formulation, the effect of axial stiffness variation in the honeycomb core on the static response of sandwich beams is investigated. It is found that due to the axial stiffness variation in the core, displacements of beams and stresses of face sheets and core are significantly affected. As such, the potential design space has been expanded by utilizing variable stiffness materials in sandwich beams.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials and their structures have received growing interest in recent decades from industries and researchers due to economic and environmental drivers. Of particular interest are laminated sandwich structures for their wide ranging applications in the aerospace, automobile and marine industries for superior structural properties combined with light weight. Furthermore, as material costs of carbon- and glass- fibre composite, and metallic and non-metallic foam/core reduce, the potential of sandwich constructions increases [1].

To fully realize the potential of sandwich structures, efficient and accurate structural analysis tools are required. Extensive literature concerning static and dynamic response of sandwich beams is readily available in Ref. [2-10]. Among available sandwich beam models, the transverse compressibility of the core is either ignored [2] or modelled using elasticity theory [3]. Rao [2] developed an analytical approach to investigate the effect of extensional and bending stiffness in a stiff core on the overall static response of the sandwich beam. Assuming that the face sheets act as Euler beams and the transversely incompressible honeycomb core behaves as a Timoshenko beam, the governing equations were derived using three field variables:

- transverse deflection of the beam,
- extension at the mid-plane of top skin,
- extension at the mid-plane of bottom skin.

With a variational method, the governing differential equations were solved via Laplace transforms. Results show that the effect of core stiffness on beam deflection and stresses can be significant for stiff-cored, thick-cored or highly unsymmetric sandwich beams. Jeon [9] presented a new formulation to

analyse the bending behaviour of tapered sandwich plates constituting an orthotropic core of unidirectional linear thickness variation and two uniform anisotropic composite skins. The minimum total potential energy method was used to derive the governing equations and approximate solutions were obtained with the Ritz method. With the geometric coupling between the transverse shear strain in the core and the normal deflection of face sheets considered, effects of edge conditions, taper ratios and stacking sequence of the laminated skins on the structural deflection were studied parametrically. In the sandwich beam model by Frostig [3], namely the higher-order sandwich panel theory, skins are modelled using Euler beam theory and the transversely flexible core is modelled with a two-dimensional elasticity theory. The bending behaviour of the sandwich beam was investigated in terms of internal stress resultants and displacements in skins, peeling and shear stresses in skin-core interfaces and stresses and displacement fields of the core. Moreover, the nonlinear displacement fields through the depth of the core was also determined.

Figure 1. Sandwich beam geometry and co-ordinates

In addition to conventional metallic, polymeric foam and core, functionally graded materials (FGM) have been used in sandwich plates recently [15-18]. FGM refers to materials of which mechanical properties vary continuously and mostly through the thickness of a structure [17, 18]. Static and dynamic response of FGM beams have received increasing attention [19-22] due to their potential for optimizing structural weight and mechanical properties. Zenkour [15, 16] systematically investigated the static and dynamic behaviours of simply supported transversely graded ceramic-metal sandwich beams. Deflection and stresses of a three-layer sandwich plate of uniform thickness were predicted using a sinusoidal shear deformation plate theory. It was found that the mechanical response of the sandwich beam was highly dependent on the FGM properties. Tounsi [17] presented a refined shear deformation theory to predict the thermoelastic bending behaviour of FGM sandwich plates. The material volume fraction was assumed to obey a power law function through the thickness of the beam and then the Young's modulus and thermal expansion coefficient were calculated via the rule of mixtures. The proposed model provided accurate results against other methods reported in the literature.

In this article, a novel layer-wise sandwich beam model is developed by extending Rao's three-layer sandwich beam theory [2]. Using the present formulations, sandwich beams using cores of axial variable stiffness have been studied and different geometries and boundary conditions are considered. In the following sections, formulations are presented in detail and results are then discussed in order to qualitatively assess the effect of axial stiffness variation in the core on the static response of sandwich beams.

2 MECHANICS OF THE SANDWICH BEAM MODEL

A sandwich beam with length (L), width (b), and core, upper and lower skins thickness of (2h_c), (2h_u) and (2h_l) respectively, is shown in Figure.1, with three local coordinate systems defined for each layer. Key assumptions are:

- 1) face sheets are made of linear elastic materials and satisfy Euler beam theory;
- 2) the honeycomb core resists through-thickness deformation and is formulated using a first order shear deformation theory;
- 3) face sheets are perfectly bonded to the core with negligible adhesive layer thickness.

2.1 Displacement fields and strains

As shown in Figure.1, displacement fields in all three layers of the sandwich beam are described using the local coordinate systems:

$$\begin{aligned} u_{x,\xi} &= u_\xi - z_\xi \varphi_\xi; \\ u_{y,\xi} &= 0; \\ u_{z,\xi} &= w_\xi \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where, $\xi=u,c,l$ refer to the upper skin, core and lower skin respectively and u, w, φ are the extensional, transverse and rotational displacement at the centroid of skins and core respectively. With the aforementioned assumptions, both the upper and lower face sheets are modelled as Euler beams, which leads to elimination of shear deformation in upper and lower skins, and through-thickness deformation is also neglected, resulting in five state variables for the beam, namely the beam transverse displacement w , the extensional displacement at the centroid of skins and core $u_{u,c,l}$, and the rotational displacement at the mid-plane of core, φ_c . Now, by applying the enforced beam geometry compatibility conditions at the upper and lower face/core interfaces, the extensional displacement at the centroid of face sheets can be explicitly expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} u_u &= u_c - h_c \varphi_c - (h_u + z_u) w'_c; \\ u_l &= u_c + h_c \varphi_c + (h_l - z_l) w'_c \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

With algebraic relations in Eq.2, the beam state functions are now further reduced to only three, namely $\{u_c, w_c, \varphi_c\}$. In this paper, the von Karman strains [25, 26] are used to account for the geometric nonlinearity of the beam under large deflections, and the only non-zero strains are:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{xx,\xi} &= \varepsilon_{xx,\xi}^0 + z \varepsilon_{xx,\xi}^1; \\ \gamma_{xx,\xi} &= \varphi_{xx,\xi}^0; \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{xx,\xi}^0 = \frac{du_\xi}{dx_\xi} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dw_\xi}{dx_\xi} \right)^2; \quad \varepsilon_{xx,\xi}^1 = \frac{d\varphi_\xi}{dx_\xi}; \quad \varphi_{xx,\xi}^0 = \frac{dw_\xi}{dx_\xi} - \varphi_\xi$$

where, $\xi=u,c,l$ refer to the upper skin, core and lower skin respectively.

Figure 2. Clamped-clamped sandwich beam subject to sinusoidal distributed load

2.2 The Ritz method

Combined with the Ritz method, the minimum total potential energy principle is applied to obtain an approximate solution of the present formulation. The total energy of the deflected sandwich beam constitutes the strain energy (U) of face sheets (Π_u, Π_l) and core (Π_c) and the potential of the external loads (Π_e), and the minimum total potential energy principle is:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(\Pi_{total}) &= \delta(U + V) \equiv 0; \\ U &= \Pi_u + \Pi_l + \Pi_c; \\ V &= \Pi_e \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The strain energy of the face sheets in Eq. (4) is derived in terms of the extensional and transverse displacement while for the core, potential energy contributed by the shear deformation has to be considered too. For laminated composite face sheets considered in this model, the layup is assumed to be symmetric and balanced and classical laminate theory is applied to calculate the skin's equivalent stiffness [23].

In the Ritz method, the displacements are expanded in series of admissible functions that satisfy the essential boundary conditions. The displacement fields of the core are assumed to be:

$$\begin{aligned} w_c(x) &= \sum_{i=1}^N a_i w_i(x) \\ u_c(x) &= \sum_{i=1}^N b_i u_i(x) \\ \varphi_c(x) &= \sum_{i=1}^N c_i \varphi_i(x) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $w_i(x)$, $u_i(x)$ and $\varphi_i(x)$ refer to the admissible functions of the transverse, extensional and rotational displacement, a_i, b_i, c_i are the unknown polynomial coefficients and N is the order of expanded functions.

Figure 3. Load-deflection diagram of Beam A

The resulting Rayleigh-Ritz parameters equation, Eq. (6), is nonlinear and is solved with iterative methods [6, 25], such as the Newton-Raphson technique. Using the Ritz method combined with Newton-Raphson technique, the minimum total potential energy principle can be re-written in the following matrix form [25,26]:

$$[K(q_i)] - [F_i] = 0 \text{ or } [R(q_i)] = 0 \quad (6)$$

where $[K]$ is the nonlinear stiffness matrix, which depends on the undetermined coefficients q_i ; $[F]$ is the generalized force vector; $[R]$ represents the residual vector or unbalanced force vector [25]. In the Newton-Raphson method, the formulations is solved by iteratively evolving the q_i , which reduces the unbalanced force vector to an acceptably small residual value, ϵ_{cri} . The solution at the (n+1)th iteration is obtained using the nth iteration solution and the tangent matrix, $[T]$,

$$\{q_i\}_{n+1} = \{q_i\}_{n+1} - [T(q_i)_n]^{-1}[R(q_i)_n] \quad (7)$$

At the beginning of the iteration, an initial solution needs to be provided, which can be arbitrary and the solution is updated at each iteration until the unbalanced force vector approaches the termination criteria. Elements of matrix $[T]$ and $[R]$ are defined in Appendix.

However, the nonlinear model can be simplified to a linear one, which only accounts for the small strain component $\epsilon_{xx,\xi}^0 = \frac{du_\xi}{dx_\xi}$, and stiffness matrix $[K]$ then becomes a linear one and Eq. 6 can be solved straightforwardly. In this paper, both the linear and nonlinear model are used for the analysis.

Figure 4. Transverse displacement of Beam A, B, C

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1 Uniform sandwich beams with clamped-clamped boundary conditions

In this section, uniform sandwich beams with both ends clamped (C-C) are studied using the present formulation. A beam configuration of length $L=200$ mm, width $b=20$ mm, face sheets thickness $h_{u,1}=0.2$ mm and core height $h_c=7.1$ mm is chosen and associated material properties are shown in Table.1. Functionally graded foams with three types of polynomial axial stiffness variation are considered while the Poisson's ratio is assumed to remain constant. As shown in Figure. 2, a sinusoidal distributed load is applied to the beam, $q(x) = q_0 \sin(x \cdot \frac{\pi}{L})$.

In this paper, Legendre polynomials are used as basis functions due to their good convergence properties for localized responses [24]. The admissible functions of displacement field are expanded in terms of normalized coordinate $\eta = (2 \cdot x/L) - 1$, ($\eta \in [-1,1]$) with C-C type boundary condition applied to the admissible functions in Eq. 5.

Figure 5. ‘Zig-Zag’ effect in the normal stress distribution along beam thickness, (MPa)

At first, the results of the present formulation, for both nonlinear (NLM) and linear models (LM) are compared against three dimensional finite element results (FEM, ABAQUS). As shown in the load-deflection diagram of the sandwich beam A, Figure. 3, the nonlinear model provides more accurate beam deflection prediction than the linear model and is subsequently used in this section.

Material	E (MPa, $x \in [0, L]$) and ν (-)	
Carbon/epoxy, [90/0/90]	-	E=56900, $\nu=0.005$
Functionally graded foam	Beam A	PVC foam, E=104, $\nu=0.3$ ^[27]
	Beam B	$E = 104 + 0.92x - 0.0046x^2$, $\nu=0.3$
	Beam C	$E = 104 - 0.68x + 0.0034x^2$, $\nu=0.3$

Table 1: Material properties for sandwich beams of C-C fixed ends

Figure. 4 presents the transverse displacement of sandwich beams A, B and C under a sinusoidal load with $q_0=14$ MPa/mm using the present nonlinear model. Results of Beam A is plotted against that from FEM and is shown to compare well with a maximum 2% error. However, although stiffness of core is much lower than that of the skin ($E_{skin}/E_{core} \approx 500$), a significant change in beam deflection has been

found in Figure.4. As expected, the in-plane stiffness variation of core considerably affects the beam's transverse displacement and a stiffer core in Beam B leads to reduction in maximum displacement, which results from an increased effective bending stiffness of the beam and a higher transverse shear modulus in the core. A contrary trend is found in Beam C which has less stiff core than Beam A and B.

With a high skin-to-core stiffness ratio in the sandwich beams, axial tensile loads are mostly carried by the skins and the layer-wise material property difference such as transverse shear and normal moduli leads to the sudden changes of normal stresses at the skin/core interfaces, which is known as the 'Zig-Zag (ZZ)' phenomenon [27]. The 'ZZ' phenomenon in the axial stress distribution through the beam thickness is shown in Figure. 5 and is in good agreement with FEM. It is shown that the axial stress in both top and bottom skins has changed due to the core's stiffness variation. As it is shown in Figure. 5, Beam B has lower axial stresses in the top skin with higher stiffness of core while Beam C presents higher top skin axial stress with lower core stiffness compared to Beam A. The reason is that for indeterminate structures such as beams with C-C boundary conditions, the stress distribution is deformation dependent and therefore, the core's property variation plays an important role in both deflection and stress distribution. Furthermore, the transverse shear stress and strain at the mid-plane of the core are also altered, as shown in Figure. 7, and the transverse shear strain is affected to a higher level as the transverse shear modulus is also changed with the in-plane stiffness.

Figure 6. Transverse shear stresses and strains at the centroid of core

3.2 Tapered sandwich beams with clamped-free boundary conditions

Sandwich plates often have non-uniform cross-sections when used in structural components like aircraft wings and control surfaces. In this section, the present formulation is used to investigate the static response of tapered cantilever sandwich beams (C-F boundary condition). The beams are of length,

$L= 100$ mm, beam width $b=20$ mm, face sheets thickness $h_{u,l}=0.2$ mm and core height at root $h_{c,root}=12.1$ mm with a taper angle $\beta = 5^\circ$, which is the angle between axial axis of face sheets and core. A transverse tip load, P_0 is applied at the free end. Three types of honeycomb core in-plane stiffness variation are considered (Beams D, E and F) and shown in Table. 2. Shown in Figure.7 is the deflection diagram of Beam D under tip load P and it shows that for C-F type beam, both LM and NLM provide accurate results, compared to FEM, in the load-deflection scope considered. However, in this section, LM is used to calculate beam responses and results are shown against that from FEM.

Figure 7. Load-deflection diagram of Beam D

Figure 8. Load-deflection diagram of Beam D

Material	E (MPa, $x \in [0, L]$) and ν (-)	
Carbon/epoxy, [0/90/0]	-	$E=109000, \nu=0.005$
Functionally graded foam	Beam D	PVC foam, $E=104, \nu=0.3$ ^[27]
	Beam E	$E = 104 + 0.3x, \nu=0.3$
	Beam F	$E = 104 - 0.8x + 0.001x^2, \nu=0.3$

Table 2: Material properties for sandwich beams of C-F ends

As shown in Figure. 8, the transverse displacement of sandwich beams under tip load $P_0 = -792$ N is a function of axial stiffness variation in the core. The tip displacement of Beam E with linearly increased axial core stiffness is reduced by 11% compared to that of Beam D of uniform core stiffness. Furthermore, Beams E and F provide tip displacements that are close in value yet the deformation shape

is considerably different from each other. Corresponding to stiffness distribution in Table. 2, Beams D, E and F show different slope distribution which results from the change of effective bending stiffness of the cross-section and also the variation in transverse shear modulus under the same tip loads.

Figure 9. 'Zig-Zag' effect in axial stresses for cantilever type beams, (Mpa)

Figure 10. Transverse shear stresses and strain at centroid of cores in Beam D, E, F

The 'ZZ' effect in axial stress in Beam D, E and F is shown in Figure. 9 and an accuracy within 1% compared to results from FEM is achieved. Similarly, the core's in-plane load-carrying capacity is negligible and most axial loads are carried by the top and bottom skins and the effect of core in-plane stiffness variation on axial stress in skins is limited, as shown in Figure. 9, which is due to the fact the variation of the core stiffness is minor compared to skin stiffness. A similar trend is found in the transverse shear stress at the mid-plane of core and no apparent effect of core stiffness variation is noticed (Figure. 10 (a)), while the transverse shear strain has been significantly affected as the shear modulus is changed along with the in-plane Young's modulus, as shown in Figure 10 (b).

4 CONCLUSION

A novel layer-wise sandwich beam formulation has been developed by extending Rao's sandwich beam model. Combined with the minimum total energy principle, the Ritz method has been applied to solve both the linear and nonlinear governing equations. Results show that the present model is capable of providing accurate predictions of static response of sandwich beams with different geometries and boundary conditions over a wide range of properties. Due to the fact that simplifications are made in beam modelling and only three field variables are used, there are indeed some effects that can't be predicted, such as the thickness direction transverse displacement in the core.

Based on the model, the effect of axial stiffness variation in the core on the beam's static response has been investigated. It was found that significant changes in the static response was achieved via tailoring the core's axial stiffness, which is also dependent on the boundary conditions. For beams with C-C boundary conditions, both stresses and displacements have been affected while for the cantilever beams, stresses are less affected considering the limited variation in core stiffness compared to skin stiffness. With variable stiffness materials utilized, the sandwich beam design space can be considerably extended and the present model can be used as a preliminary design tool for laminated sandwich beams.

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APPENDIX

Elements of the residual vector $[R]$ and the tangent matrix $[T]$ are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_i &= \frac{\partial \Pi_{total}}{\partial a_i}, i = 1, \dots, N; \\
 R_i &= \frac{\partial \Pi_{total}}{\partial b_{i-N}}, i = N + 1, \dots, 2N; \\
 R_i &= \frac{\partial \Pi_{total}}{\partial c_{i-2N}}, i = 2N + 1, \dots, 3N; \\
 T_{i,j} &= \frac{\partial R_i}{\partial a_j}, i = 1, \dots, 3N; j = 1, \dots, N; \\
 T_{i,j} &= \frac{\partial R_i}{\partial b_{j-N}}, i = 1, \dots, 3N; j = N + 1, \dots, 2N; \\
 T_{i,j} &= \frac{\partial R_i}{\partial c_{j-2N}}, i = 1, \dots, 3N; j = 2N + 1, \dots, 3N;
 \end{aligned}$$

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